

THE EFFECT OF BOOKCREATOR.COM ON VOCABULARY LEARNING IN A VIETNAMESE LOWER SECONDARY SCHOOL

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Abstract: *This study investigates the impact of the interactive website Bookcreator.com on vocabulary learning among Grade 8 students in a lower secondary school in Thai Nguyen City, Vietnam. Using an action research design over twelve weeks, the study integrated Bookcreator.com into classroom instruction. Data were collected through pre- and post-tests, a student questionnaire, and semi-structured interviews. Results indicated a statistically significant improvement in students' vocabulary retention (memory and recall of words) after the intervention, as well as increased engagement and motivation (emotional and motivational involvement). Although the absence of a control group limits causal claims, the study achieved its objective of evaluating the tool's effectiveness in a Vietnamese EFL context, showing promise as a learner-centered tool for vocabulary learning..*

Keywords: *Bookcreator.com, vocabulary learning, digital tools, student engagement*

1. Introduction

In the digital age, the integration of technology into language education has transformed traditional instructional approaches, emphasizing more interactive, personalized, and student-centered learning environments (Godwin-Jones, 2018). Among the core language skills, vocabulary acquisition plays a foundational role in developing learners' overall communicative competence, affecting reading comprehension, listening proficiency, and writing fluency (Nation, 2001; Schmitt, 2008). However, conventional vocabulary instruction methods, such as rote memorization and textbook-based exercises, often lack engagement and fail to promote long-term retention (Mayer, 2020).

Digital tools that support multimodal and active learning have been shown to enhance vocabulary learning outcomes. According to Dual coding theory (Paivio, 1990) and Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning (Mayer, 2014), presenting words through both visual and verbal channels can improve learners' memory and recall by activating multiple cognitive pathways. Moreover, digital platforms that enable students to create their own content foster a constructivist learning environment, where learners are actively involved in making meaning, rather than passively receiving information (Bruner, 1996; Vygotsky, 1978).

Bookcreator.com, a web-based tool for creating interactive digital books, has emerged as a promising application in this context. By allowing students to incorporate images, audio recordings, and video clips alongside textual content, the platform supports creative expression and personalized learning, key factors that contribute to deeper engagement and improved vocabulary retention (Kearsley & Shneiderman, 1998; Fitriya, 2024).

This study aims to examine the effectiveness of Bookcreator.com in supporting vocabulary learning for Grade 8 students at a lower secondary school in Thai Nguyen, Vietnam. It addresses the need for context-specific research on educational technology implementation in Vietnamese EFL (English as a Foreign Language) classrooms and investigates how digital book creation may foster vocabulary retention, engagement, and motivation in young learners.

In addition, although global research has demonstrated the benefits of technology integration in language learning, there remains a need to strengthen evidence specific to the

Vietnamese context. Previous local studies (e.g., Lê Quang Minh, 2016; Vũ Thị Hương, 2020) have shown positive impacts of ICT and multimedia tools on vocabulary learning, but research on Bookcreator.com itself remains limited in Vietnam. Moreover, this study distinguishes between engagement - defined as students' emotional and motivational involvement - and retention - referring to their ability to recall and use newly learned vocabulary over time. This distinction is essential for understanding how digital tools can address both affective and cognitive dimensions of learning.

The present study aimed to address the following research questions:

(i) To what extent does the use of the interactive website *Bookcreator.com* influence students' vocabulary retention?

(ii) What are students' perceptions of the use of the interactive website *Bookcreator.com*?

2. Theoretical framework and literature review

2.1. Theoretical framework

This study is underpinned by three key theoretical perspectives that collectively explain the mechanisms through which Bookcreator.com can enhance vocabulary learning: Dual coding theory, Constructivist learning theory, and Engagement theory.

According to Paivio's (1990) Dual coding theory, human cognition involves two distinct but interconnected systems for processing information - one for verbal representations and one for non-verbal (mainly visual) stimuli. When learners receive vocabulary input through both textual and visual modalities, such as words accompanied by images or audio, they develop stronger mental associations, thereby improving memory retention and recall (Clark & Paivio, 1991; Mayer, 2014). Bookcreator.com facilitates this process by allowing students to pair new vocabulary with multimedia elements, aligning well with the principles of this theory.

In parallel, constructivist learning theory, as proposed by Piaget (1970) and Vygotsky (1978), emphasizes that learning is an active and meaning-making process. Learners construct knowledge through interactions with content, peers, and their own prior experiences. In this context, Bookcreator.com empowers students to design their own digital books, which not only personalizes learning but also encourages deeper cognitive engagement through the creation of meaningful, self-directed learning artifacts. Vygotsky's notion of the zone of proximal development also supports the collaborative potential of such tools, where learners scaffold each other's understanding through shared digital projects. Complementing these cognitive and developmental frameworks, Engagement Theory (Kearsley & Shneiderman, 1998) asserts that students learn more effectively when involved in authentic, interactive, and collaborative tasks that promote sustained attention and intrinsic motivation.

By offering opportunities for personalization, creativity, and social sharing, Bookcreator.com embodies the core tenets of engagement theory, fostering learner autonomy and emotional investment in the vocabulary learning process. It is important to note that in this framework, engagement and retention represent distinct but related outcomes. Engagement refers to learners' emotional and motivational involvement in the learning task, while retention denotes their ability to remember and apply the newly acquired vocabulary over time. This study considers both dimensions essential to understanding the effectiveness of Bookcreator.com.

2.2. Literature review

A growing body of research has underscored the pedagogical value of multimedia tools in vocabulary instruction, particularly within EFL contexts. Mayer (2014), drawing on his Cognitive theory of multimedia learning, emphasized that students learn more effectively when instructional materials present both verbal and visual information, as this dual-channel processing enhances

cognitive integration and memory retention. Similarly, Clark and Paivio (1991), through the lens of Dual coding theory, demonstrated that multimodal input reinforces linguistic information, thereby facilitating more durable vocabulary learning. Building on these theoretical foundations, several empirical studies have explored the application of interactive digital tools in EFL classrooms. For instance, Oktavia and Nurhayati (2023) investigated the use of Bookcreator.com in blended learning environments with Indonesian secondary students and reported that learners exhibited higher motivation and improved vocabulary acquisition. Likewise, Fitriya (2024) developed Bookcreator-based e-modules for TOEFL preparation and found that the platform enhanced learners' autonomy and comprehension of academic vocabulary. These findings affirm the tool's potential to support both general and test-oriented vocabulary instruction. Within the Vietnamese educational context, digital innovations have also received growing attention. Lê Quang Minh (2016) highlighted the effectiveness of information and communication technology (ICT) integration in promoting vocabulary retention, while Vũ Thị Hương (2020) confirmed that the use of multimedia-enhanced learning tools significantly improved university students' vocabulary performance. In addition, recent Vietnamese studies have explored the use of various digital tools to support vocabulary learning. Hà Thị Huyền (2020) highlighted that using Kahoot in university English classes increased student engagement and improved vocabulary recall. Nguyễn Thị Hồng Minh and Đặng Thảo Nguyên (2024) demonstrated that integrating Wordwall activities into Grade 10 lessons helped students expand vocabulary and sustain interest in learning. Nguyễn Thúy Ngọc and Trần Thanh Nga (2024) reported that online multiplayer games boosted university students' motivation to learn new vocabulary through interactive and collaborative environments. Nguyễn Thị Hồng Mến (2025) conducted a large-scale survey among university students and instructors, showing that digital technologies, including online platforms and mobile apps, enhanced engagement and long-term retention of English vocabulary despite some technical challenges. Despite these encouraging results, relatively few Vietnamese studies have focused specifically on Bookcreator.com as a learning platform.

3. Methodology

This study adopted an action research design, which is particularly suited for classroom-based interventions aiming to improve teaching practices and student learning outcomes (Burns, 2010). The research was conducted over a twelve-week period at a lower secondary school in Thai Nguyen City, Vietnam, and involved a purposive sample of 40 Grade 8 students aged between 13 and 15 years. The primary objective was to evaluate the effectiveness of Bookcreator.com in enhancing vocabulary learning among EFL learners. The intervention required students to create personalized digital books using Bookcreator.com, in which they integrated newly learned vocabulary with multimedia elements such as images, audio, and video. To assess learning outcomes, pre-tests and post-tests were administered to measure changes in vocabulary retention. Vocabulary items were selected from the curriculum and reflected topics relevant to daily communication. In addition to quantitative data, a student questionnaire was used to gather perceptions on usability, engagement, and motivation associated with the platform. The questionnaire employed a 5-point Likert scale and was validated through expert review to ensure content reliability. The questionnaire included 12 items covering engagement, usability, and learning experience. Internal consistency was acceptable, with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.82. A limitation of this action research design was the absence of a control group, which restricted the ability to make strong causal claims about the intervention's effectiveness. This limitation is acknowledged and further discussed in the Conclusion section. To gain deeper insights into the students' experiences, semi-structured interviews were conducted with a subset of participants.

These interviews explored learners’ attitudes, challenges, and perceptions of the impact of Bookcreator.com on their vocabulary development. The use of mixed methods - quantitative testing, surveys, and qualitative interviews - allowed for a more comprehensive understanding of the intervention’s effectiveness and its reception by learners (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018). All participants and their guardians provided informed consent, and ethical procedures were followed to ensure student anonymity and voluntary participation.

4. Findings and discussion

4.1. Findings

4.1.1. Impact of interactive website Bookcreator.com on students’ vocabulary retention

Vocabulary retention refers to the ability of learners to remember and use newly acquired words over time. To assess long-term retention, the study compared students' performance on vocabulary tests administered before and after the intervention. Short-term retention was evaluated through weekly class activities that required students to apply new vocabulary in digital projects.

The results of the vocabulary tests revealed a clear improvement. Before the intervention, the students' mean score on the vocabulary pre-test was 7.93 (SD = 1.70), indicating a moderate command of the target vocabulary. Following six weeks of Bookcreator.com-enhanced instruction, the mean post-test score rose to 9.40 (SD = 1.69). The difference between pre-test and post-test scores was examined using a paired-sample t-test, which demonstrated a statistically significant increase in vocabulary knowledge ($t(39) = -18.45, p < .001$). These results provide empirical evidence that the use of Bookcreator.com had a positive effect on long-term vocabulary retention.

Table 1.

Paired-sample t-test results for vocabulary retention

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	SD	SEM	95% confidence interval of the difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Pre-Test Score - Post-Test Score	-1.475	.506	.080	-1.637	-1.313	-18.446	39	.000

Short-term vocabulary retention, though not measured through interim tests, was inferred through classroom observations and analysis of student work. Throughout the intervention, students were observed correctly reusing newly introduced vocabulary in their digital books, oral presentations, and peer feedback. This consistent application suggests active cognitive processing and consolidation of vocabulary in meaningful contexts, consistent with Schmitt’s (2008) findings that productive use strengthens retention.

Interview data also supported these quantitative findings. Students frequently noted that multimedia features - such as images and recorded audio - made words easier to remember. For example, one student shared, “*The pictures and audio helped me remember the words better.*” Another commented, “*Adding my own pictures and voice made it easier to memorize.*” These experiences reflect the principles of Dual Coding Theory (Paivio, 1990), which suggests that memory retention is enhanced when information is encoded both visually and verbally. Moreover, students’ ability to create personalized books aligns with constructivist theories that emphasize learning through active engagement and content creation (Bruner, 1996; Vygotsky, 1978).

However, a few challenges were noted, particularly in the early stages of using the platform. Some students struggled with navigation and integrating multimedia components, which occasionally disrupted the learning process. As one student noted, *“At first, I wasn’t sure about it... it was confusing how to start”*. These challenges point to the importance of initial scaffolding and clear guidance when introducing digital platforms to learners (Warschauer & Meskill, 2000).

In short, the integration of Bookcreator.com into vocabulary instruction had a demonstrably positive impact on both short-term and long-term vocabulary retention. The platform’s interactive, multisensory design supported deeper learning through engagement, contextual application, and student autonomy. With appropriate support during onboarding, Bookcreator.com has strong potential to enhance vocabulary acquisition in EFL settings.

4.1.2. Students’ opinions on the use of the interactive website Bookcreator.com

To gain comprehensive insights into students’ perceptions of Bookcreator.com in vocabulary learning, the study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative survey data with qualitative interview responses. The results revealed five primary thematic areas reflecting students’ experiences: engagement and motivation, multisensory learning, creativity and autonomy, learning experience, and usability.

A notable finding from the analysis was the positive influence of Bookcreator.com on student engagement and motivation. As shown in Table 2, the mean score for the item *“Using Bookcreator.com increased my motivation to learn new vocabulary words”* was 2.83 (SD = 1.466), suggesting moderate agreement across the sample.

Table 2.

Descriptive statistics of students’ opinion on engagement and motivation

N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
40	1	5	2.83	1.466

Interview responses reinforced this finding, with students expressing that the opportunity to create personalized digital books sparked interest and made the learning process more enjoyable. One student noted, *“Creating my own book with pictures and voice made learning feel fun and motivating.”* However, a few students experienced a decrease in enthusiasm over time, reporting that the novelty wore off and the process began to feel repetitive. This feedback indicates the importance of integrating more varied or dynamic tasks to sustain long-term motivation. In addition to engagement, the multisensory nature of Bookcreator.com was widely appreciated. Students were able to interact with vocabulary through text, images, audio, and video, facilitating multiple modes of input and recall. Table 3 shows a mean score of 2.75 (SD = 1.256) for the effectiveness of multimedia features in supporting vocabulary learning, reflecting generally positive attitudes.

Table 3.

Descriptive statistics of students’ opinion on vocabulary learning

N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
40	1	5	2.75	1.256

Interview comments such as *“Seeing the word with pictures and hearing it helped me remember”* confirmed that this multisensory input was helpful for many learners. The platform also promoted creativity and autonomy, allowing students to select vocabulary, organize content, and personalize their digital books. As presented in Table 4, students rated their overall vocabulary learning experience with Bookcreator.com at a mean of 3.00 (SD = 1.340).

Table 4.

Descriptive statistics of students’ opinion on learning experience

N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
40	1	5	3.00	1.340

Interview responses suggested that this autonomy increased students' connection to the material. For example, one student explained, *"I felt ownership of what I made, which helped me focus on the words."* Nevertheless, a few students expressed the desire for more contextual application, such as using vocabulary in writing or conversation tasks, to reinforce their learning further. Despite the overall positive feedback, the study also revealed several challenges related to usability. Table 5 shows that students gave a moderate mean score of 3.12 (SD = 1.381) regarding the ease of using Bookcreator.com, with varied experiences reported.

Table 5.

Descriptive statistics of students' opinion on usability

N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
40	1	5	3.12	1.381

Some students initially found the interface confusing and needed time to adapt. For instance, one student commented, *"The first time I used it, I didn't know how to add images or audio. But after trying a few times, it became easier."* Others experienced technical difficulties, including slow loading and media errors, which disrupted their workflow. These observations suggest that while Bookcreator.com is generally accessible, improvements in technical stability and user instructions would enhance the learning experience, particularly for students less familiar with digital platforms.

In summary, students generally viewed Bookcreator.com as a valuable and engaging tool for vocabulary learning. Its interactive and multisensory features, combined with opportunities for personalization, contributed to increased motivation, deeper vocabulary retention, and learner autonomy. However, maintaining engagement over time and resolving usability issues remain important considerations. Enhancing instructional scaffolding, diversifying task types, and integrating real-world language practice could further strengthen the platform's impact and usability in future implementations.

4.2. Discussion

The findings of this study demonstrate that integrating Bookcreator.com into vocabulary instruction significantly enhanced students' vocabulary retention and overall learning experience, and these results align well with prior research both internationally and in the Vietnamese context. The statistically significant improvement in post-test scores reflects not only the effectiveness of Bookcreator.com in reinforcing vocabulary through repeated and meaningful exposure but also underscores the importance of learner engagement and autonomy.

Similar studies, such as those by Oktavia and Nurhayati (2023) and Fitriya (2024), reported comparable gains in vocabulary acquisition when using Bookcreator in EFL settings, suggesting a broader applicability of the tool across diverse learning environments. The interactive and multimodal nature of the platform - incorporating text, visuals, audio, and personalization - allowed students to process new vocabulary more deeply, which supports the claims of Mayer (2014) and Clark and Paivio (1991) regarding the cognitive benefits of multimedia input. In line with constructivist learning theory (Piaget, 1970; Bruner, 1996), students in this study actively constructed knowledge by designing their own digital books, engaging in tasks that were not only academically relevant but also personally meaningful.

This mirrors previous findings by Draper and Brown (2004), who emphasized that student-generated content increases motivation and conceptual understanding. Students' comments about enjoying the freedom to choose images or record their own voices also reflect key principles of

Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000), which highlights autonomy as a driver of intrinsic motivation. Despite these strengths, some technical challenges were reported, including navigation issues and platform lags, echoing usability concerns found in studies by Kuo (2013) and Garrison and Cleveland-Innes (2005). Moreover, a few students indicated that repetitive task formats reduced their interest over time - a pattern similarly observed by Fitriya (2024) - suggesting that long-term use may benefit from more varied activities and collaborative features. Overall, the results of this study not only reinforce the theoretical benefits of multimedia and student-centered learning but also extend previous research by providing context-specific evidence of how Bookcreator.com can effectively support vocabulary development in Vietnamese lower secondary EFL classrooms.

It is also important to clearly differentiate between engagement and retention in interpreting these findings. Engagement refers to students' emotional and motivational involvement in learning tasks, as seen in their enjoyment and sense of autonomy when creating digital books. Retention, on the other hand, describes their ability to remember and apply newly learned vocabulary over time, as evidenced by the statistically significant improvement in test scores. By addressing both dimensions, this study provides a more comprehensive understanding of how Bookcreator.com supports vocabulary learning in EFL contexts.

5. Conclusion

Bookcreator.com proves to be an effective and promising tool for vocabulary instruction in EFL contexts, particularly among lower secondary learners. Its interactive and multimodal features - allowing for the integration of text, images, audio, and personalized content - significantly foster student engagement, autonomy, and deeper cognitive processing of vocabulary. The findings of this study indicate that students not only retained new words more effectively but also found the learning process more enjoyable and meaningful. These outcomes highlight the pedagogical potential of digital book-making platforms in shifting vocabulary instruction toward more learner-centered and constructivist approaches. However, the study's relatively small sample size and short intervention period limit the generalizability of the results. Additionally, the absence of a control group restricts the ability to make strong causal claims about the intervention's effectiveness. Future studies should consider experimental or quasi-experimental designs to address this limitation and to provide stronger causal evidence of effectiveness.

Overall, this study achieved its primary objective of evaluating the effectiveness of Bookcreator.com in supporting vocabulary learning among Grade 8 EFL students, demonstrating statistically significant improvements and positive student perceptions. Future research should investigate the long-term impact of Bookcreator.com on vocabulary development, explore its effectiveness across different age groups and proficiency levels, and compare its performance with other digital tools to identify the most effective strategies for integrating technology into vocabulary teaching.

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